

AGRIPRENEURSHIP EMPOWERMENT AND LIVELIHOOD OF VICTIMS OF INSURGENCY IN BORNO STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The prevalence of insecurity in Nigeria is a matter of utmost concern. Particularly, the problem of insurgency in Borno State in North-Eastern Nigeria has lasted for over two decades, resulting in a large number of displaced persons who were mostly farmers and traders but lost farmlands, relatives, and businesses. The Borno State government's move to resettle victims and relocate them to a more stable life prompted this inquiry into the impact of agribusiness empowerment on the livelihoods of victims of insurgency and the socioeconomic impact of insurgency on victims in Borno State. This study employed linear regression and descriptive analysis in SPSS to analyse data from questionnaires administered to victims of insurgency in Borno State in 2025. The study found that agripreneurship empowerment, income, and employment had positive effects on victims' livelihoods, but the effects of income and employment were not significant. The study also found that the victims' income, savings and social lives were adversely affected by the insurgency. It is therefore recommended that agripreneurship empowerment be increased to boost income, employment, and the welfare of victims; secondly, technology should be deployed to curb insurgency, so that its negative impact on the socioeconomic life of victims can be mitigated or eliminated.

Keywords: Insurgency, Agripreneurship, Internally Displaced Persons, Livelihood.

JEL Codes: D74, H12, H53, J19, I3, Q13

1. INTRODUCTION

Insecurity distorts economic activities and economic performance. Insecurity in Nigeria ranges from terrorism, insurgency, kidnapping, banditry, cattle rustling, farmer-herder clashes, to incessant agitations by ethno-cultural and religious groups. Over the past decade terrorist attacks have been prevalent in the North East, particularly Borno State, has experienced terrorist attacks that have undermined economic activities. The activities of several terrorists have led to death, displacement, looting of agricultural output and injuries to victims. Population displacement is triggered by terrorism, contributing food insecurity and poverty. Despite security efforts marred by other the challenges to empowerment. McAullife and Oucho (2024) noted that in Nigeria, 3,646,000 persons were internally displaced in 2022 due to conflict and violence. Similarly, the Nigeria Assessment and Analysis Working Group (AAWG, 2023) indicated that in 2023, 2.2 million were displaced in the northeastern Nigeria

of which Borno State accounted for 82% (1.8 million). These displaced persons no longer have access to their extensive farmland. Displacements due to conflict and violence are expected to translate into complex negative implications for the people.

Agripreneurship is agricultural entrepreneurship that does not necessarily require ownership of a large expanse of land for agricultural practices, making it critical for improving the livelihood of displaced victims of insurgency. In an attempt to make a living and improve their livelihoods, these victims of insurgency pursue new sources of income, including agricultural entrepreneurship. It involves the development of entrepreneurial skills in agriculture, such as cropping and animal husbandry, fish farming, poultry, cattle rearing and exploring the value chain through processing and marketing these agricultural products. The need to diversify the economy prompted an increase in agripreneurship, which has also been promoted among victims of insurgency.

To improve the living conditions of the people, the Borno State Government (BSG) rolled out a plan to relocate victims of insurgency by building new homes and providing facilities. A lot has been achieved by the BSG towards the relocation plan of the BSG to close Internally Displaced Persons' (IDP) camps by 2027, through establishment of resettlement areas and the return of IDPs closer to their place of origin; AAWG (2023) reported that 17 IDP camps out of the 215 IDP camps housing 372,139 households was closed at Jere, Konduga, Ngala and Maiduguri Metropolis by the BSG as at June 2024. Due to these camp closure targets and the critical role of agripreneurship empowerment in the livelihoods of victims of insurgency, this study examined the relationship between agripreneurship empowerment programmes and the livelihoods of victims of insurgency in selected local government areas of Borno State.

The problem of insurgency in North East Nigeria and particularly in Borno State is often attributed to Boko Haram and the Islamic State of West African Province. According to Amnesty International (AI, 2018), more than 10,000 armed terrorists operated in Borno State; about 500 villages and 13,000 hectares of farmland have been devastated by the terrorists. The terrorists killed about 2,830 people between 2011 and 2018 in incessant attacks. The number of children orphaned as a result of such attacks has reached about 40,000 since 2010, and over 16,000 people have been internally displaced. The disruption of rural economic activities, the primary means of rural livelihood in the State, has been a matter of critical concern. Aside from the ultimate prize of death, for survivors or victims of insurgency, the incidence of insurgency is a devastating new beginning marked by the losses, including: communal origin, farmland, livestock, family members, income source, social support, and freedom. However, the impact of agripreneurship empowerment on the livelihoods of victims of insurgency remains an empirical gap (Abubakar & Amurtiya, 2023; Dan, 2020; Adelaja & George, 2019; Abdurashid, Saifullahi & Amir, 2018; Issa, Abah & Amalu 2015). Studies by Odunze (2019) and Quadri, Silwal, Archibong and Jibrilla (2024) on agripreneurship analysed intervention programmes for the empowerment of victims but did not specifically investigate the impact of these programmes on the livelihoods of victims of insurgency in Borno State.

Hence, the impact of agripreneurship empowerment on victims of insurgency in Borno State remains unclear. It is against this backdrop that this research is set to assess the impact of agripreneurship empowerment on the livelihood of victims of insurgency in Borno State and examine the socioeconomic impact of insurgency on these victims. This study is therefore structured into five sections comprising: introduction; conceptual and empirical literature review; methodology and theoretical framework; results and discussion of findings; conclusion and policy recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Agripreneurship Empowerment

Adeyanju, Mburu, Gituro, Chumo, Mignouna, and Muliganya (2023) conceptualize agripreneurship as a profitable linkage between agriculture and entrepreneurship in which innovative and creative approaches to agricultural activities are employed to enhance farm businesses and maximize profit. Similarly, Addo (2018) defines agripreneurship as identifying and seizing an opportunity (problem, idea, business, or market imbalance) in the agri-food space to organise resources to convert it into solutions. Similarly, according to Orisaremi, Ahmadu and Orisaremi (2022), agripreneurship is the process of adopting new techniques in agriculture or its allied sectors to improve output and economic earnings; it converts agricultural activity into an entrepreneurial endeavor.

In other words, Quadri et al. (2024) explained that agripreneurs increase productivity and discover new methods to add value through innovation. Agricultural entrepreneurship offers direct and indirect opportunities across various agricultural activities. On the other hand, empowerment is the process of increasing capacity to choose and transform lives (Babu, 2014). Empowerment improves skills and people can be empowered by themselves or by powerful individuals, groups, or governments. Agripreneurship empowerment involves supporting victims of insurgency by equipping them with agricultural and entrepreneurial skills to build profitable businesses.

2.1.2 Livelihood

According to the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 2022), livelihood comprises capabilities, assets and activities required for a means of living. In other words, Isyaku, Gyong and Ahmed (2023) defined livelihood as the means of securing the basic needs of life, taking into account economic and non-economic factors. Similarly, Saleh and Fidelis (2025) defined livelihood as the means by which individuals and households secure essentials such as food, income and shelter through their resources, skills and social support. Ali and Ali (2024) observed that IDPs adopted and adapted new livelihoods, including agricultural activities, handicrafts, and small-scale retail, to survive in the new environment. Livelihood in this study refers to the economic recovery of victims of insurgency.

2.1.3 Insurgency

Isyaku et al. (2023) defined insecurity as a state of uncertainty that exposes individuals to danger. Insurgency differs from terrorism in the sense that the insurgents attempt to control territories while terrorists instill fear in the people, yet both constitute insecurity. Aminu (2023) observed that, despite the government's efforts, insecurity is on the rise. Vulegbo, Umaru, Yakatun, and Makun (2025) defined terrorism as a systematic use of the threat of violence to communicate a political message rather than to defeat an opponent. Ugwuoke (2022) opined that terrorism in Nigeria encompasses political, religious and economic dimensions.

Insurgents may employ terrorism as a strategy to attain their aim. Peverga, Aye-Agele, Udele, and Iorliam (2025), Abakpa (2021) and Ndubeze-Ogaraku and Onoja (2017) viewed insurgency as an act of rebellion against the legitimate authority by an illegitimate group. Adamu, Abdullahi, and Mustapha (2023) viewed insurgency as a struggle to control contested political spaces. Saleh and Fidelis (2025) specifically conceptualized book haram as employing bombings, kidnappings and assassinations to destabilize northeastern Nigeria and undermine government authority. Obi-Egbedi and Owosho (2023) posit that insurgency in the North East

exerts pressure on the already fragile resource environment. Insurgency in this study refers to the heinous activities of armed groups in the North East of Nigeria, specifically in Borno State.

2.2 Empirics

Several studies have focused on the effect of insurgency on labour supply, food security, and agriculture (output, development, productivity, investment and income) (Abubakar & Amurtiya, 2023; Chiwuzulum & Uwaifo, 2021; Adelaja & George, 2019; Sidney, Hayatudeen & Kwajafa, 2017). These studies found a negative impact of insurgency on these variables. Ohida (2023) focuses on humanitarian logistics of relief materials rather than agripreneurship empowerment.

Other studies focused on agripreneurship and examined its challenges, relationship to rural youth and perceptions. Yoganandan, Rahman, Vasan and Meero (2022) examined agripreneurs' satisfaction and found that demographic and socioeconomic factors significantly affected agripreneurs' satisfaction. Akumbom, Egwu and Shillie (2023) investigated the impact of agripreneurship on poverty reduction in Cameroon. A mixed-methods design was employed, with data gathered through questionnaires from 384 households in Tubah Sub-division, North West region, analysed using partial least squares. Attitudes towards agripreneurship, innovative behaviour and the need for achievement had a positive effect, while inheritance of family ventures and start-up motives had a negative effect on poverty reduction.

Broadly, Peverga et al. (2025) found that terrorism impacted Real Gross Domestic Product negatively in the short run and in the long run; while Abakpa (2021) used secondary data and found that insurgency affected socioeconomic activities, Ndubueze and Onoja (2017) found that agricultural livelihoods are negatively affected by the degradation of the environment and insurgency in Nigeria. Similarly, Ugwuoke (2022) concludes that insecurity beclouds the Nigerian State. Saleh and Fidelis (2025) found that disruptions in food production, rising food prices, and shortages are significantly associated with food insecurity; hence, insurgency has worsened food availability, production challenges and market stability, and has negatively impacted food production. Despite using primary data, Saleh and Fidelis (2025), however, sampled Maiduguri, Bama and Gwoza in Borno State. Adamu et al. (2023) found a negative impact of insurgency on scavengers' income in Borno State, while Isyaku, Gyong and Ahmed (2023) found that insecurity negatively impacted respondents' livelihoods in Kastina State.

Oduze (2019) reviewed the Nigerian Agricultural Promotion Policy (APP) and found that it recognizes the inherent constraints affecting entrepreneurship in the sector. Whereas Quadri et al. (2024) identified Borno State and Adamawa States as focal States where the USAID Feed the Future Nigeria Integrated Agriculture Activity exists and employed a questionnaire and a descriptive method of frequencies and tables, they found that participants had a positive opinion of the programme, indicating that production as a result of training is excellent. Further data analysis revealed that knowledge and skills in the use of knapsack sprayers, pesticide mixing, and business management had improved. Oduze (2019) and Quadri et al. (2024), having focused on the APP and USAID Feed the Future Nigeria Integrated Agriculture Activity, respectively, indicating that a literature gap exists in examining the impact of intervention programmes on affected communities, particularly in Borno State. Closely linked to this study is the study of 19 African Countries by Adeyanju et al (2023) which revealed that participation in agripreneurship significantly increased income and improved food security.

The reviewed empirical studies are relevant to this study, as they either focused on agripreneurship or insurgency; however, the impact of agripreneurship empowerment on

victims of insurgency remains to be investigated. This study will therefore improve on the existing literature by critically examining the role of agripreneurship in the livelihoods of insurgency victims through agripreneurship empowerment in Borno State.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Study Area, Population and Sample Size

The study area is Borno State, which consists of 27. The three geopolitical zones of Borno North, Central and South have nine LGAs each: Borno North has Abadam, Gubio, Guzamala, Kukawa, Magumeri, Marte, Mobbar, Monguno and Nganzai; Borno Central comprises of Bama, Dikwa, Jere, Kaga, Kala/Bage, Konduga, Mafa, Maiduguri and Ngala; Borno South consists of Askira Uba, Bayo, Biu, Chibok, Damboa, Gwoza, Hawul, Shani and Kwaya Kusar. The multistage sampling procedure includes purposive sampling of large resettlement areas and IDP camps in the three geopolitical zones of the state, namely Borno North, Central and South.

The study population is based on the International Organisation for Migration [IOM] (2023) record that North-East Nigeria has a total of 2,375,661 internally displaced persons in 483,467 households, with Borno State accounting for 82% of displaced persons which is 1,948,042. Based on the Krejcie and Morgan formula the sample size is 385 but to optimize precision, the sample of 500 internally displaced persons were selected.

Considering that Borno State accounts for the highest percentage of IDPs in North East Nigeria and the increasing incidence of insurgency from 2025 to 2026, 500 questionnaires were administered, but 495 were retrieved. Kukawa and Abadam LGAs from the North, Maiduguri from the Central, and Biu from the South were purposively selected, and 500 structured questionnaires were randomly administered in November, 2025. Due to the high intensity of insurgency in Borno North, the questionnaires were administered on 200 victims of insurgency in Kukawa and 100 victims in Abadam, Maiduguri, and Biu (LGA), Borno State, respectively. This is backed by the fact that the North has high intensity attacks and that the report by IOM in 2024 on camp closure by Local Government Area (LGA)s in Borno State identified Kukawa as having the highest number of 30,462 relocated IDPs, while Maiduguri, being the administrative, military and humanitarian headquarters of the state, has a large number of IDPs. Biu is considered relatively secure, peaceful and business inclined for IDPs.

3.2 Theoretical Framework

The research will be guided theoretically by Amartya Sen's 1998 capability approach, which argues that expanding human capabilities and freedom enhances livelihoods and welfare. Having categorized freedom opportunities into political, economic, social, transparency guarantees and protective security, it was concluded that the provision of freedom and resources will enhance choices to reach full potential (Sen, 2000). Specifically, protective security is the system of social safety nets that prevents a group affected by poverty from suffering terrible misery. The theory posits the existence of differential abilities and the possibility of converting the same resources into more valuable functioning. Functioning include working, resting, being literate, being healthy, being part of a community and being respected (Robeyns, 2003). The relevance of the capability approach to this study lies in its capacity to enhance control over economic circumstances. The theory emphasizes that the ability to act is based on skills acquired and that lost ability can be restored through

enhancement; hence, the impact of agriprenuership empowerment on victims of insurgency can be evaluated within the framework of Sen's capability approach.

3.3 Methods and Model Specification

A mixed-methods research design, combining descriptive and inferential statistics, was applied. Descriptive analyses using frequencies and percentages were employed to analyse categorical and continuous data. For the regression analysis, the model by Akumbom et al. (2023), which specified poverty reduction (PR) as a function of agriprenuership (ENT), was adapted. Considering that poverty reduction measures livelihood, this model is further modified to include social and economic factors in place of social opportunities and economic facilities, as suggested by Sen's approach that these categories of freedom determine livelihood, thus:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \mu$$

Where the dependent variable Y is the livelihood of victims of insurgency, X_1 is agriprenuership empowerment of victims of insurgency, X_2 is social factor, X_3 is economic factor, Δ = coefficients and μ = error term.

3.4 Variable Measurements and Explanation

The livelihood of victims of insurgency is measured by how agrpreneurship has helped in the economic recovery of victims which had response options of: yes, significantly; yes, moderately; no impact and not applicable. With 120 and 179 respondents representing 21.3% and 31.8% asserting to yes, significantly and yes, moderately respectively. This implies that agriprenuership empowerment has helped most the respondents recover economically which depicts the livelihood of victims and serves as the dependent variable of the model.

The independent variables are determined by the Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The agriprenuership empowerment construct consist of the support received (training, start-up capital, tools/equipment, seed/livestock, market access and none), aid from agriprenuership (generated income, improved food security, developed new skills, increase confidence and reintegrated into community), frequency of engaging in agriprenuership activity (regularly, weekly/monthly, occasionally, rarely and not at all) and sustainability of agribusiness (very sustainable, somewhat sustainable, not sustainable and not sure). The PCA indicate reliability of the construct with the cumulative percentage of total variance explained of 62.953, the sampling adequacy of 0.573 Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test statistics and probability value of the Bartlett's test at 0.00 which is less than 0.05. The Eigenvalues of 1.488 and 1.030 implies that 2 component is selected as indicated by the elbow rule on the scree plot. the component matrix indicate agriprenuership aid and support are extracted the two highest components at 0.717 and 0.719 respectively while communalities of 0.767 for support received by victims is the highest indicating complete explanation of the agriprenuership empowerment factor.

Figure 1 Scree Plot of the Agripreneurship Empowerment Variable

Note. Authors' computation from SPSS 2026

The social factor comprising marital status, education level, social life and relation/community standing is unreliable as the PCA indicates 0.503 measure of adequacy in the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test statistics and probability value of the Bartlett's test of less than 0.001 suggesting component is reliable for interpretation. The scree plot shows that 2 components of marital status and how insurgency affects social life are extracted at Eigenvalues of 1.390 and 1.021 with 60.821% cumulative loadings of total variance explained. This implies that the social factor is reliable.

Figure 2 Scree Plot of the Social Factor

Note. Authors' computation from SPSS 2026

The economic factor is determined by current employment, current monthly average income, compared income and compared savings by which the PCA confirms the validity of the construct indicating 0.600 Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test statistics and probability value of the Bartlett's test below 0.001 which is less than 0.05. The scree plot shows that 2 components are extracted confirming the Eigenvalue of 1.751 and 1.001 are greater than 1. The cumulative percentage loadings of the extracted components amount to 68.792 implying that the economic factor is reliable.

Figure 3 Scree Plot of the Economic Factor

Note. Authors' computation from SPSS 2026

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Impact of Agripreneurship Empowerment on the Livelihood

To assess the impact of agripreneurship empowerment on the livelihood of victims of insurgency in Borno State, Table 1 shows the regression results:

Table 1 Agripreneurship and Livelihood Model Summary

R²	Adjusted R²	Standard Error	Durbin-Watson Statistics
0.194	0.187	0.903	1.636

Note. Authors' computation from SPSS 2026

Table 1 shows the regression results, with an R² of 0.194 and an adjusted R² of 0.187, indicating a poor fit. However, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.636 which is approximately 2 indicates that the residuals are not autocorrelated but a desirable outcome for the model.

Table 2 ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Significance
Regression	67.996	3	22.665	27.809	0.000
Residual	282.004	346	.815		
Total	350.000	349			

Note. Authors' computation from SPSS 2026

Despite the model having a poor fit as indicated by Table 1, the ANOVA Table 2 shows an F-statistic of 27.809 and probability value of 0.000, indicating overall statistical significance of the regressed model.

Table 3 Regression Results on the Coefficients of Determination of the Livelihood of Victims

Variables	Coefficients	Significance	Correlation	Collinearity	
			Partial	Tolerance	VIF
Constant		0.000			
X₁	0.316	0.000	0.330	0.988	1.013
X₂	0.314	0.000	0.325	0.966	1.035
X₃	0.027	0.583	0.030	0.955	1.047

Note. Authors' computation from SPSS 2026

Table 3 presents the coefficients for the independent variables that determine economic recovery among victims of insurgency in Borno State. The coefficients of determination for agripreneurship empowerment (0.316), social factor (0.314) and economic factor (0.027) have a positive relationship with economic recovery, as theoretically expected and found by Akumbom et al., (2023). Though confirming the pooled result for Kenya, Nigeria and Uganda by Adeyanju et al (2023), agripreneurship empowerment and economic factor have p-values of less than 0.000, indicating statistical significance at the 5% level contradicting the non-significant result for Nigeria found by Adeyanju et al (2023), which may be due to the prevalence of insecurity/ insurgency in Nigeria. The social factor is not statistically significant with probability value of 0.583 which is not farfetched from restricted social activities due to insurgency in Borno State. Hence a unit increase in agripreneurship empowerment and the economic indicator improves the livelihoods of Victims by 31% each.

4.2 Post Estimation Tests

The test for autocorrelation is already established by the Durbin-Watson statistic in Table 1, which indicates, in the table, the absence of autocorrelation, a desirable result.

4.2.1 Multicollinearity Test

From table 3, the partial correlation of agripreneurship empowerment, income and employment are 0.281, 0.022 and 0.021 respectively. are low, which is also supported by the collinearity statistics, where the Tolerance values of 0.990, 0.880, and 0.888 are greater than 0.20, indicating no multicollinearity. The VIFs of 1.011, 1.137, and 1.126 confirm the absence of multicollinearity.

Table 4 Collinearity Daignostics

Dimension	Eigenvalue	Condition Index	Constant	Variance Proportions		
				X ₁	X ₂	X ₃
1	1.222	1.000	.01	.11	.30	.38
2	1.050	1.079	.52	.36	.07	.00
3	.936	1.142	.47	.38	.20	.00
4	.791	1.243	.01	.15	.43	.62

Note. Authors' computation from SPSS 2026

Of the four dimensions of variance proportions measured, dimension 1 and 4 shows that X₃ varies at 0.38% and 0.62% while dimensions 2 and 3 shows X₁ vary at 0.36 and 0.38, respectively; these are below the 0.90 threshold as the eigenvalues of 1.222, 1.050 and 0.936 are not as close to zero as dimension 4. Similarly, the condition indices of 1, 1.079, 1.142, and 1.234 are below the threshold of 15, indicating the absence of multicollinearity.

4.2.2 Normality Test

Figure 4 Histogram of Residuals

Note. Authors' computation from SPSS 2026

The histogram in the figure indicates a bell-shaped distribution of the residuals, suggesting that the model residuals are normally distributed, as required.

4.2.3 Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 5 ZPRED and ZRESID Scatterplot

Note. Authors’ construction from SPSS 2026

The distribution on the scatterplot indicates constant variance, a desirable result indicating the absence of heteroscedasticity.

4.3 Socioeconomic Impact of Insurgency on Victims of Insurgency

Descriptive statistics including tables, frequencies and percentages were used to analyse respondents’ views. There are indications of missing values because not all questionnaires were returned and not all respondents answered all questions as presented below:

Table 6 Compared to before the insurgency, how would you describe your current income level?

Responses	Frequencies	Percentages
Not applicable (never had income before)	100	17.8%
Much lower	189	33.6%
Slightly lower	62	11.0%
About the same	19	3.4%
Slightly higher	71	12.6%
Much higher	39	6.9%
Missing System	83	14.7%

Note. Authors’ computation from SPSS 2026

Table 6 indicates 33.6% of respondents' current income levels are much lower than before the insurgency. Implying negative impact of insurgency on victims as found by Isyaku et al (2023).

Table 7 Compared to before the insurgency, how would you describe your current savings level?

Responses	Frequencies	Percentages
Much lower	289	51.3%
Slightly lower	73	13.0%
About the same	68	12.1%
Slightly higher	18	3.2%
Much higher	23	4.1%
Missing System	92	16.3%

Note. Authors’ computation from SPSS 2026

Table 7 confirms results from Table 6, as current savings of 51.3% of respondents is much lower.

Table 8 How has the insurgency affected your social life or wellbeing?

Responses	Frequencies	Percentages
Displacement from community	151	26.8%
Loss of social support	125	22.2%
Psychological stress	148	26.3%
Reduced community participation	49	8.7%
Others	9	1.6%
Missing	81	14.4%

Note. Authors' computation from SPSS 2026

On the opinion of respondents on the effect of insurgency on social life and wellbeing, the highest percentages of 26.8% and 26.3% respondent indicates that these victims of insurgency have been mostly affected by displacement from communities and psychological stress, respectively. Also of key focus is the 22.2% of respondents who have lost social support. Reduced community participation accounts for 8.7% of respondents which may be attributed to the insecurity situation in the study area and the high rate of displacement from their community of origin. Other unspecified ways in which insurgency has affected social life and wellbeing accounts for 1.6% of respondents.

Hence, the socioeconomic impact of insurgency on victims, as perceived by respondents, is negative, as the increased incidence of insurgency has reduced their income and savings to levels well below pre-insurgency levels. In addition, they have been displaced from their communities, lost social support, psychologically stressed, experienced less community participation and other forms of social disruption which were not disclosed.

Table 9 What are the major challenges you face in agripreneurship?

Responses	Frequencies	Percentages
Lack of capital	136	24.2%
Insecurity	138	24.5%
Market access	46	8.2%
Inadquate training	38	6.7%
Lack of land /inputs	31	5.5%
Poor infrastructure	33	5.9%
Others	8	1.4%
Missing	133	23.6%

Note. Authors' computation from SPSS 2026

Lack of capital and insecurity accounts for 24.2% and 24.5% of responses as the major challenges faced by these victims. Market access accounts for 8.2% of responses. Other respondents attribute 6.7% to inadequate training, 5.5% to lack of land or inputs, 5.9% to poor infrastructure and 1.4% to other unspecified challenges. It can be inferred from the above that the major challenges faced by these victims are inadequate capital and insecurity.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

In line with Akumbom et al., (2023), this study found a positive effect from agripreneurship empowerment of victims, social and economic factors and concludes that agripreneurship empowerment and economic factor significantly improves livelihood. However, the positive effect of the social factor on livelihood was found to be insignificant which may have resulted from minimal social activities as result of insurgency.

This study also found that the socioeconomic impact of insurgency on victims is negative as found by Peverga et al (2025) and Abakpa (2021) in other studies thus confirming the results by Adamu et al (2023) that insurgency negatively impacted the income of scavengers in Borno State. This study also found that the major challenges confronting victims include lack of capital, insecurity, market inaccessibility, inadequate inputs, loss of land and reduced communal participation. Thus confirming findings by Isyaku et al. (2023) that insecurity had negative impact on the livelihood of respondents in Kastina State.

This study concludes that insurgency has made life worse for victims; and that agripreneurship empowerment and other economic factors positively impacts economic recovery of victims of insurgency in Borno State. It is therefore recommended that more victims should be empowered to increase their participation in agripreneurship to improve their livelihood; and it is also recommended that the use of technology to combat insurgency will help to mitigate or eliminate the negative socio-economic impact of insurgency and other challenges on victims of insurgency in Borno State.

Conflict of Interest:

No conflict of interest.

Data:

Questionnaire administration.

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